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Species Composition of Freshwater Snails Across Six Local Government Areas in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Freshwater snails serve as intermediate hosts for several snail borne parasitic diseases, such as schistosomiasis and fascioliasis. This study aimed at assessing the species composition, of freshwater snails in six Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Bayelsa State, during June, 2023 and February, 2024. Snails were collected and identified following a standard procedure. A total of four thousand, seven hundred and twenty-two fresh water snails in seven genera were identified. The species composition in the order of their increasing abundance are: *Lymnaea natalensis* (45.44%), *Melanoides spp* (21.48%), *Onchomelania spp* (9.99%), *Bulinus globosus* (4.96%), *Bulinus natalensis* (2.23%), *Biomphalaria spp* (2.47%) and *Pumata maculatus* (2.14%) respectively ($p > 0.05$). When the Fresh water snails collected from the study communities were pooled into LGAs, *Lymnaea natalensis* ($n = 2012, 44.7%$) was more abundant in all the six LGAs, followed by *Melanoides spp* ($n = 1040, 23.1%$) in five LGAs. Others were; *Bulinus globosus* ($n = 419, 9.32%$) abundant in four LGAs, *Onchomelania spp* ($n = 484, 10.7%$) found in four LGAs. *Biomphalaria spp* ($n = 120, 2.7%$), *Bulinus natalensis* ($n = 108, 2.4%$) and, *Pumata maculatus* ($n = 94, 2.1%$) were exclusive in one LGAs respectively ($p > 0.167$). The presence of these vector snails in four of the six LGAs indicates potential endemic zones for schistosomiasis and fascioliasis. The findings have underscored the ecological heterogeneity and species-specific habitat preferences across of fresh water snail in Bayelsa State.

Keywords: Freshwater snails, Species composition, Malacological survey, Bayelsa State, Nigeria,

INTRODUCTION

Freshwater snails are ecologically and medically significant in tropical and subtropical ecosystems. As benthic invertebrates, they play vital roles in aquatic food webs, and serve as bioindicators of environmental healthiness (Pointier, 2020). More importantly, several of the freshwater snail species act as intermediate hosts for parasitic trematodes causing diseases such as schistosomiasis and fascioliasis (WHO, 2020; Ekpo et al., 2021). Schistosomiasis alone affects over 250 million people worldwide, with Nigeria bearing the highest burden in Africa (Akinwale et al., 2015; Adenowo et al., 2022).

Freshwater bodies provide an ideal breeding habitats for a variety of snail species due to favorable hydrological conditions, vegetation cover, and organic nutrient inputs (Nwoko et al., 2016). The role of freshwater has been pivotal in the transmission and dynamics of snail borne diseases. Bayelsa State, is

characterized by network of rivers, streams, swamps, and wetlands, which have provided a conducive environment for the growth and proliferation of the snails. However, environmental degradation arising from oil exploration, agricultural runoff, and rapid urbanization has significantly altered aquatic ecosystems in diverse places, potentially influencing the diversity and distribution of snail populations (Olalekan *et al.*, 2020; Ekiye & Zejiao, 2022).

Studies on the distribution on the fresh water snails in Bayelsa State remain limited. Existing research has often been localized (Amawulu, & Assumpta, 2021; Amawulu & Akpoebiere, 2022) and lacks comparative multi-site analysis (Ezenduka *et al.*, 2023). Understanding the current distribution species composition of the freshwater snail across multiple Local Government Areas (LGAs) is essential for developing targeted vector control strategies and supporting integrated disease management programs. This study therefore investigates the species composition and relative abundance of freshwater snails across six LGAs in Bayelsa State with the aim of providing updated, location-specific data on snail distribution. The outcome is expected to aid public health officials, ecologists, and environmental managers in designing effective interventions of snail borne diseases

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted in six Local Government Areas (LGAs) within Bayelsa State, Nigeria: Yenagoa, Ogbia, Ekeremor, Kolokuma/Opokuma, Sagbama, and Southern Ijaw. Bayelsa lies in the heart of the Niger Delta and is characterized by a tropical rainforest climate with extensive water bodies including rivers, creeks, swamps, and floodplains. These features provide suitable habitats for freshwater snail proliferation. The climate consists of two major seasons: the rainy season (April to October) and the dry season (November to March), which influence water levels and snail distribution.

Sampling Design

A cross-sectional survey was conducted across the six LGAs between June and October 2023, during the rainy season when aquatic snail populations typically peak. Sampling sites were selected purposively based on proximity to human settlements, presence of freshwater bodies, and accessibility. At least two freshwater sampling sites (e.g., ponds, riversides, irrigation channels) were surveyed per LGA.

Snail Collection

Snail collection was carried out using standard scooping and hand-picking methods (WHO, 2011). A long-handled scoop net (mesh size: 0.5 mm) was used to sample snails from aquatic vegetation, muddy banks, and submerged substrates over a period of 30 minutes per site. Collected snails were placed in labeled plastic containers with wet cotton wool to retain moisture and transported to the laboratory for identification.

Identification and Classification

In the laboratory, snails were rinsed with clean water and sorted by morphological characteristics using hand lenses and identification keys (Brown, 2001; Kristensen, 2021). Species were identified based on shell shape, size, color, aperture, and coiling.

Data Recording and Analysis

The total number of each species was recorded per LGA. The relative abundance of each species was calculated as the proportion of a species' count to the total number of snails collected in each LGA. Data were tabulated and visualized using Microsoft Excel 365. A stacked horizontal bar chart was created to represent the species composition across the LGAs, aiding in spatial comparison. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize species distribution. No inferential statistics were applied as the study focused primarily on observational spatial distribution. However, species dominance and exclusivity within LGAs were noted for ecological interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

Although the study involved no human or vertebrate animal subjects, verbal consent was obtained from local authorities and residents before sampling. The study was approved by the Department of Biological Sciences, [Your Institution Name], and aligned with ethical guidelines for ecological fieldwork.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of four thousand, seven hundred and twenty-two fresh water snails in seven genera were identified morphologically. The species composition in the order of their increasing abundance are: *Lymnaea natalensis* (45.44%), *Melanoides spp* (21.48%), *Onchomelania spp* (9.99%), *Bulinus globosus* (4.96%), *Bulinus natalensis* (2.23%), *Biomphalaria spp* (2.47%) and *Pumata maculatus* 2.14%) respectively ($p > 0.05$) fig. 1. When the Fresh water snails collected from the study communities were pooled into LGAs, *Lymnaea natalensis* (n= 2012, 44.7%) was more abundance in all the six LGAs, followed by *Melanoides spp* (n= 1040,23.1%) in five LGAs. Others were; *Bulinus globosus* (n=419,9.32%) abundant in four LGAs, *Onchomelania spp* (n= 484,10.7%) found in four LGAs. *Biomphalaria spp* (n=120,2.7%), *Bulinus natalensis* (n=108,2.4%) and, *Pumata maculatus* (n=94, 2.1%) were exclusive in one LGAs respectively. Differences in species abundance across LGAs were not significant ($p > 0.167$) table 1. Although *Lymnaea natalensis* was highest across LGAs, the snail abundance varied across LGAs. *Lymnaea natalensis* distribution were; Ekeremor (79.8%), Yenagoa (71.2%), southern Ijaw (54.0%), kolokuma/opokuma(44.9%), Ogbia(28.0%) and Sagbama(26%) respectively. *Melanoides spp* was highest in Ogbia(61.1%), followed by southern ijaw (37.5%) and least in sagbama (1.4%). The percentage abundance of *Onchomelania spp* in sagbama, kolokuma/opokuma, Ekeremor and southern ijaw were (28.1%,23.9%,14.8% and 2.1%) respectively. *Bulinus globosus* were more abundant in Sagama (24.1%) and least in Yenagoa (0.3%). However, *B. natalensis* and *Biomphalaria spp* were exclusive in Yenagoa while *Pumata maculatus* was exclusive in Ogbia. Differences in species abundance across LGAs were significant ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 1: species composition of fresh water snails collected during June, 2023 and February, 2024

Table 1: species composition of fresh water snails across LGAs

LGAs	N	NO (%)						
		Snail species						
		<i>Bulinus globosus</i>	<i>Bulinus natalensis</i>	<i>Lymnaea natalensis</i>	<i>Pumata maculatus</i>	<i>Melanoides spp</i>	<i>Onchomelania spp</i>	<i>Biomphalaria spp</i>
SOUTHERN IJAW	1118	71(6.4)		603(54.0)		419(37.5)	23(2.1)	
SAGBAMA	983	240(24.1)		256(26.0)		14(1.4)	276(28.1)	
KOLOKUMA/ OPOKUMA	519	107(20.6)		233(44.9)		55(10.6)	124(23.9)	
EKEREMOR	411			328(79.8)		22(5.4)	61(14.8)	
OGBIA	867			243(28.0)	94(10.8)	530(61.1)		
YENAGOA	798	2(0.3)	108(13.5)	568(71.2)				120(15.0)
TOTAL	4506	419(9.3)	108(2.4)	2012(44.7)	94(2.1)	1040(23.1)	484(10.7)	120(2.7)

DISCUSSION

The present study has provided a current information of freshwater snail species composition, in six Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Bayelsa State. Seven species were identified: *Lymnaea natalensis*, *Melanoides spp.*, *Oncomelania spp.*, *Bulinus globosus*, *Biomphalaria spp.*, *Bulinus natalensis*, and *Pumata maculatus*. The population distribution observed in this present study highlight the diversity freshwater snail ecology in the Niger Delta region. Onyekachi *et al.*, (2023) in KwaZulu-Natal (KZN) province of South Africa recorded eight freshwater snail species (*Biomphalaria pfeifferi*, *Bulinus globosus*, *Lymnaea natalensis*, *Tarebia granifera*, *Bulinus tropicus*, *Bulinus forskalii*, bivalves, and *Physa acuta*). However, Perissinotto, et al. (2014) who reported 12 snail species during the biodiversity census performed in Lake St. Lucia, is imangaliso Wetland Park was two-fold more than the snail species reported in this present study.

Lymnaea natalensis emerged as the most dominant species, occurring in all six LGAs and accounting for the highest overall abundance in this present study. Its ubiquity supports highlights its ecological plasticity and ability to thrive in a wide range of freshwater habitats, (Utzing et al., 2003). Previous research confirms the dominance of *L. natalensis* in Nigerian freshwater environments (Idowu et al., 2022). *Melanoides spp.* showed significant presence in Ogbia and Southern Ijaw, with moderate representation in Ekeremor and Kolokuma/Opokuma. These snails are known bioindicators of water quality and prefer sandy or muddy substrates with clean, oxygen-rich water (Pointier, 2001). Their abundance in these LGAs is an indication that the environment may be a periphyton-rich habitats, which may have provided adequate food sources and breeding grounds. The distribution of *Melanoides spp* was patchy and stable in this study. It is evident that wherever found, *Melanoides* they outcompete the indigenous snail species (Pointier, 2001). They are known to serve as intermediate host for more than six parasitic diseases Interestingly, *Oncomelania spp.*, though generally less abundant, was heavily concentrated in Sagbama and Kolokuma/Opokuma. This genus is more commonly associated with East Asia. Its identification warrants further genetic verification possibly initiating adaptability to a tropical region. *Bulinus globosus* and *Biomphalaria spp* are both recognized vectors of human schistosomiasis. *B. globosus*. They were found in three LGAs (Kolokuma/Opokuma, Sagbama, and Southern Ijaw), while *Biomphalaria spp.* was restricted in Yenagoa. The focal distribution of these species highlights potential hot spots for urogenital and intestinal schistosomiasis transmission. The limited spread of *Biomphalaria spp.* may be attributed to its higher sensitivity to environmental pollutants, pH changes, and habitat disturbances (Brown, 2001; Ekpo et al., 2010). Given the endemicity of schistosomiasis in Nigeria (WHO, 2023), the presence of these vector snails demands regular snail control programs and public health awareness in the study areas.

The identification of *Pumata maculatus* exclusively in Ogbia, although in low numbers, introduces an additional layer of interest. It may reflect a localized distribution due to unique microhabitat conditions or limited sampling periods. This species has received little attention in West African malacology, and further ecological studies are necessary to determine its role in freshwater ecosystems.

CONCLUSION

This study has highlighted the diversity and distribution of freshwater snails across six LGAs in Bayelsa State. Seven species, with *Lymnaea natalensis* being the most prevalent was identified. The presence of vector snails such as *Bulinus globosus* and *Biomphalaria spp.* and *Lymnaea natalensis* in study areas indicates the potential public health risks, particularly schistosomiasis and fascioliasis transmission. The findings emphasize the need for regular malacological surveillance and targeted control interventions to mitigate disease spread and preserve aquatic ecosystem health.

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